

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUTUKU****FIRST NAME: TIMOTHY****PROGRAM CODE: DIDOL****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 99%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 11

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Planning and Structure (EUCLID 2025, 10-11)
2. Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper (EUCLID 2025, 12-14)
3. Punctuations (Dashes, Hyphens and Ellipsis) (EUCLID 2025, 18-20)
4. Style Guide - The Need for it (EUCLID 2025, 40-42)
5. Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) (EUCLID 2025, 43-54)

FOUNDATIONS OF PAPER WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In this response paper for period one, I will outline the key points and concepts from my perspective of the ACA-401D Course pack (Period 1). I must mention that it was a key eye-opener, especially for anyone like me who finds it easy to explain ideas and thoughts in layman's language and writing, but has to now do it within the guidelines of professional and academic writing. This paper will cover arguments on easy writing, including the rule of thumb for writing a paper, a few interesting punctuations, as well as a discussion on style guides and my prior experience with them and finally, the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) of which I think, will be beneficial when writing Major Papers (MJ) and subsequent Thesis.

2) ESSAY PLANNING AND STRUCTURE

Writing is only easy if you are writing notes from a class or a meeting session, mainly because it is for individual reference, and there are very few, if any, rules to follow. Academic or scholarly writing, on the other hand, should have a uniform approach in all

components, including citations and references to other works (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 7). This is because academia is a global field to which we all contribute through written ideas and concepts. Therefore, a strong pointer is uniformity in global and international collaboration. Before writing about any topic of interest, it is crucial to research thoroughly to have a clear understanding of the subject matter, which will, in turn, help you brainstorm and create mind maps for your arguments.

I found the section on the structure of essay writing quite intriguing in that the key components – introduction, body, and conclusion have some similarities with essay paragraphs. In both, you should start by stating the main idea/objectives, followed by supportive sentences and analysis. Finally, a critical conclusion forms the body or evidence provided (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 10-11). Although all three essay structure sections are equally important, I think the conclusion plays a big role in ensuring that the reader goes home with a summary of the main points as broadly discussed throughout the other sections. This structure reminds me of a lesson plan for a class/lecture session that promoted pedagogy.

3) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

Writing is easier said than done, and even harder to make operational (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 13). It was comforting to come across such a statement; it made me feel like I am in good company and that I am not the one who struggles with professional writing. The rules of thumb make writing a little more scientific and less abstract. One of the points that I also found to be easier said than done is writing without leading or concluding with sweeping generalities. It is easy for a statement like "Man is born free, but is everywhere in chains" to find itself in writing, although it is probably not scientifically proven. We tend to resolve some common phrases that add nothing to the core issue and may become a distraction instead (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 13).

a) Supporting assertions with seriousness

I think the issue of leading statements can easily be resolved by carefully supporting any assertions that a writer intends to portray. This way, the writer is tied to only statements that have some strong backing and can be supported professionally through citations. They need to be careful not to submit a paper with so many quotations (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 14).

If a researcher comes across a concept that they don't understand or they tend to differ from the philosophers, they should assume that they have not understood the point and try to place themselves in the shoes of that philosopher. It is important to note that the articles and books we refer to have taken time to build and create, and it would be foolish to brush them off. This calls for an exerted effort to dig deeper and try to understand those concepts that seem difficult for us to understand.

b) Do not plagiarize

Plagiarism is a major issue when it comes to academic and professional writing. I came across it twice, as a section within this topic – Rules of thumb, and as a stand-alone chapter later in the course pack. I think the main reason behind this is to promote personal thinking and take advantage of other people's works without citing them as references. It is one of the main downfalls that undermines academic integrity by devaluing an author's efforts.

Plagiarism can be avoided by properly citing the author or source that has provided the information you are using (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 34). With well-done in-text citations and a list of words cited, the rest involves proper punctuation to avoid plagiarism. The manual way of achieving this can be cumbersome and a lot of work; however, with software such as Zotero, the process becomes easier and less manual. It gives the writer more time to focus on the research and worry less about forgetting a colon or semicolon when doing the citations. It's not always that we have to cite every statement; some statements are common knowledge and can be found in numerous areas, and therefore, there is no need to cite them (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 37)

4) PUNCTUATIONS (DASHES, HYPHENS, AND ELLIPSIS)

Of all the punctuation marks in the course pack, I found the m-dash, n-dash, hyphen, and ellipsis interesting to learn, and I think I have not been using them exhaustively. The main challenge is actually keying them in using a computer keyboard. I have always used the hyphen in places where the m-dash and n-dash should be used. For example, a writer may find themselves using a hyphen to link two-part sentences, while this should be done using an n-dash instead (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 20). This could be attributed to the fact that the hyphen is readily available on a computer keyboard compared to the dashes.

5) STYLE GUIDE - THE NEED FOR IT

By using a style guide, writers can enhance the uniformity brought about by the need for academic and professional writing. As many creative writers may not see the need for a style guide and rely on their ability to follow a standard English writing style (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 41), they may find themselves in situations where a lot of effort is needed to ensure consistency. I have used style guides before when creating guides for online course development, which qualifies as technical writing, and therefore, I know firsthand how useful style guides can be from a technical perspective. Just as there are different types of written papers, there are also different course types, but a style guide gives a uniform touch to each one regardless of the subject matter. Good examples of style guides include Strunk's "The Elements of Style," which is freely available on their website

and provides style and submission guidelines for contributors to follow (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 42), The Chicago Manual of Style, and the BBC News style guide, which is in British English.

6) **CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE**

The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) provides a solid understanding of the core principles behind the Chicago style, precisely its use in academic writing, publishing, and professional documentation. It clarifies key formatting rules, citation methods, and best practices for writing in the Chicago style. The guide outlines when it is best to use abbreviations and when it is best to spell things out. Other aspects, such as capitalization, which may follow the three forms: Full caps, heading caps, and sentence caps (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2025, 45), and Consistent referencing styles are also well outlined by the CMS.

7) **CONCLUSION**

The ACA-401D course pack was as helpful as it was interesting to read. If well applied, it makes academic and professional writing much easier. I have learnt that effective essay writing starts with planning. By following an outlined structure, sticking to the key rules of thumb, and avoiding plagiarism by ensuring proper citation and referencing, it is possible to write useful academic papers.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

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